

AQLES: Probing Transformer Hidden States to Decode Quality Ranking Geometry

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Abstract

We fit linear probes on frozen transformer hidden states to test whether graded quality judgments are encoded in representational geometry. The setup uses 200 English words spanning five quality tiers, embedded in controlled sentence templates, with word-level GroupKFold cross-validation that prevents leakage between train and test. We probe DistilBERT, BERT-base, GPT-2, the Pythia suite (70M to 1.4B parameters), XLM-RoBERTa, and Phi-3-mini. Quality is decodable across all models. GPT-2 reaches $R\text{-squared} = 0.88$ on held-out words. Phi-3-mini reaches 0.926. A pattern we did not anticipate: lower-quality tiers are more geometrically separable than higher-quality tiers, with ratios between 1.2x and 1.44x in English. A TF-IDF analysis of Wikipedia contexts finds no distributional basis for this asymmetry ($p = 0.69$). Probing Pythia-70M across training checkpoints places its emergence at step 512, before quality encoding is itself reliable. The effect diminishes from 1.41x to 1.09x as models scale from 70M to 1.4B. Cross-lingual probing on French and Spanish (lexicons of roughly 100 words, not independently validated) suggests the pattern extends beyond English, though magnitudes vary (FR 2.0x, ES 3.3x) and these numbers should be treated with caution given the small and unvalidated lexicons. The mechanism producing the asymmetry remains unknown.

1. Introduction

Probing classifiers have become a standard tool for investigating what transformers encode in their hidden states. Work in this area has identified linear subspaces corresponding to syntactic structure [7], sentiment polarity [16], and factual knowledge. Most evaluative probing, however, stops at the binary level: positive vs. negative. Human quality judgments are finer-grained than that. *Mediocre* and *adequate* occupy different positions on an evaluative scale, and the distance between them is not the same as between *adequate* and *outstanding*.

Whether transformers represent this graded structure is, to our knowledge, untested. We built AQLES (Affective Quality Layer-Encoded Scoring) to find out. The framework is simple: Ridge probes at every layer of a frozen model, trained on a controlled quality lexicon. The part that turned out to matter most was the cross-validation scheme. GroupKFold with `word_id` as grouping key ensures that all templates of a test word are held out together. In early experiments without this constraint, we observed inflated scores that reflected template memorisation rather than quality encoding. Once we fixed the leakage, scores dropped but the core finding held.

We expected quality to be decodable. It is. What we did not expect was a consistent asymmetry: negative quality tiers are easier to separate than positive ones, across every model, layer, and language tested. We first observed this on DistilBERT and assumed it was model-specific. Running BERT-base showed the same pattern. So did GPT-2. Then Pythia at three scales. Then XLM-RoBERTa in three languages. Then Phi-3-mini after RLHF. After six rounds of experiments we have a robust observation and no complete explanation.

While this work was in progress, Sofroniew, Kauvar et al. [14] published a study of emotion concept representations in Claude Sonnet 4.5. Their finding that emotion geometry is organised along valence and arousal axes parallels what we observe for quality (PC1 captures 96.7% of trajectory variance in our setup). They include causal steering experiments. We do not. We cover training dynamics, cross-lingual replication, and scaling behaviour. They do not. The two studies converge from different angles on a related observation: evaluative structure in transformers is linearly organised and more robust than either group initially expected.

2. Method

Lexicon. 200 English words distributed across five quality tiers (40 per tier). Tier boundaries: Terrible (below 0.15), Mediocre (0.15 to 0.44), Good (0.45 to 0.77), Excellent (0.78 to 0.89), Exceptional (0.90 and above). Continuous scores were calibrated against the NRC Valence-Arousal-Dominance lexicon [8], which provides crowdsourced human ratings for 20,000 words. We did not conduct independent human annotation. The scores reflect the author's judgment, checked for consistency against NRC VAD. No sensitivity analysis was performed on tier boundaries or individual scores. This is a limitation: shifting "masterful" from 0.97 to 0.92 might change tier assignment, and we have not tested how much results depend on such choices.

For cross-lingual experiments (V6), French and Spanish lexicons of approximately 100 words each were constructed by the author. Neither was reviewed by a native-speaker linguist. Given the sensitivity of cross-lingual comparisons to lexicon quality, the multilingual results should be interpreted accordingly.

Templates. Each word appears in 10 sentence templates, always in predicative adjectival position: "*The overall quality of this work is {word}.*" Five templates use neutral framing, five use institutional/peer-review framing. This yields 2,000 probing sentences. Variance decomposition: template identity contributes 0.002% of total variance; word identity accounts for 98.4%. The syntactic uniformity is both a strength (controlled context) and a weakness (no test of attributive or subject-position uses).

Models. Primary: DistilBERT (66M parameters), BERT-base (110M), GPT-2 (117M). Extended: Pythia-70M, 410M, 1.4B for training dynamics and scaling; XLM-RoBERTa for cross-lingual; Phi-3-mini (3.8B, RLHF-trained) and Qwen2.5-0.5B. Encoders use mean-pooling over non-padding tokens. Decoders use last-token pooling. All decoders have pad_token set to eos_token. This fix was missing in early V3 runs, causing the 1.4B Pythia model to fail on all checkpoints.

Probing protocol. At each layer, hidden states are z-scored per feature. Ridge regression with alpha selected from [0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 100, 500, 1000, 2000, 5000] via GroupKFold (k=5). The grouping key is word_id. Classification uses logistic regression (C=1.0). Non-contextual baselines (TF-IDF, bag-of-words) achieve 20% accuracy (chance for five tiers) and R-squared near zero.

Negativity ratio (H5). We compute Cliff's delta for all 10 tier pairs at each layer. The ratio is mean $|\delta|$ for lower pairs (T0-T1, T0-T2, T1-T2) divided by mean $|\delta|$ for upper pairs (T2-T3, T2-T4, T3-T4). Values above 1.0 indicate greater separability for negative quality. One concern we have not resolved: Tier 0 scores are concentrated between 0.01 and 0.05, while Tier 4 scores span 0.90 to 1.00. This difference in score dispersion could mechanically inflate the lower-tier delta. A control with equalized within-tier variance has not been run.

3. Results

3.1 Core probing (V1).

Metric	DistilBERT	BERT-base	GPT-2
Best CV R-sq	0.656 (L5)	0.750 (L11)	0.880 (L9)
Best Accuracy	79.3%	83.5%	88.5%
H5 ratio	1.44x	1.31x	1.20x
Crystal	L1-L2 (2.4x)	L2-L3 (3.6x)	L0-L1 (8.9x)
Freq-err rho	0.332***	0.190**	0.027 (n.s.)

Table 1. V1 results. Seed variance = 0.0000 across all models.

Figure 1. Top-left: GPT-2 layer-wise decodability. Top-right: negativity ratio across architectures. Bottom-left: crystallisation profile. Bottom-right: three-model R-squared comparison.

Seven pre-registered hypotheses (H1 through H7) are confirmed within this setup. Quality decodability increases with depth (Kendall tau = 0.77 to 0.91, $p < 0.001$). All layers exceed chance. Nine of ten tier pairs show large effect sizes (Cliff's delta > 0.474). The exception is Excellent vs. Exceptional (delta = 0.10), which remains inseparable across all models. PC1 of the trajectory matrix captures 96.7 to 97.2% of variance, indicating near-unidimensional quality unfolding.

GPT-2 outperforming both encoders is the result we verified most carefully. We re-ran the pipeline, checked pooling strategies, and confirmed the train-test split. The numbers are stable. A decoder with causal attention encodes quality better than models with full bidirectional context. Additionally, GPT-2 shows no frequency-error correlation ($\rho = 0.027$, $p = 0.71$), meaning rare words like *irreproachable* are encoded as accurately as common ones. BERT and DistilBERT do not share this property ($\rho = 0.19$ to 0.33 , $p < 0.01$). We do not understand why autoregressive training produces this advantage.

3.2 Distributional analysis (V2).

We tested one candidate explanation: that negative quality words appear in more constrained contexts in the training corpus. If *terrible* appears mostly in complaints while *stellar* appears in diverse settings, the distributional structure alone could explain the asymmetry.

For each word with at least five Wikipedia occurrences (171 of 200 words), we extracted sentence contexts, vectorised with TF-IDF, and computed mean pairwise cosine similarity within each word's context set. Higher similarity means lower diversity. Tier 0 contextual diversity: 0.985. Tier 4: 0.983. Spearman rho between tier and diversity: -0.03, $p = 0.69$.

No relationship. The direction, if anything, is opposite to the hypothesis. This rules out the TF-IDF-based distributional account, though it does not rule out more sophisticated measures (e.g. contextual embedding diversity, syntactic frame variation). The question of why models develop the asymmetry remains open.

3.3 Training dynamics (V2).

We probed Pythia-70M at 15 checkpoints from step 0 (random initialisation) to step 143,000 (final model). At step 0: R-squared = 0.04, H5 = 1.13x. Essentially random. At step 512: H5 jumps to 1.89x, but R-squared is only 0.12.

This was the finding that required the most verification. The model appears to develop the evaluative asymmetry before it can encode quality reliably. We re-ran this checkpoint, checked the probing pipeline for off-by-one errors, and ran a permutation control. The pattern held. By step 1,000 the bias peaks. Then it gradually recedes: 1.54x at step 5,000, 1.41x at step 143,000.

3.4 Scaling (V2).

Model	R-squared	H5 ratio
Pythia-70M	0.662	1.41x
Pythia-410M	0.920	1.13x
Pythia-1.4B	0.954	1.09x

Table 2. Quality improves and bias diminishes with scale.

Two observations from three data points (which limits how much can be claimed). First, R-squared increases substantially from 0.66 to 0.95. Second, H5 drops from 1.41x to 1.09x. The bias does not disappear entirely, even at 1.4B parameters. Whether this trend continues at larger scales is an open question we cannot test on free-tier Colab.

Figure 2. Negativity ratio across three architectures.

3.5 Head attribution (V3).

Per-head probing on Pythia-70M shows that five attention heads carry 80.3% of the asymmetry excess (measured as the sum of per-head Cliff's delta above a uniform baseline). On Pythia-410M, the top five heads account for 22.5%. This shift from localised to distributed is itself notable, though we cannot fully rule out that extraction quality differs between the two model sizes.

Peak H5 occurs at training step 1,000 on both 70M and 410M. The relative training step is 0.7% in both cases. Whether this constitutes a genuine developmental milestone or a coincidence across two data points is impossible to determine without additional model sizes. The 1.4B model, which could have strengthened this claim, failed due to a tokenizer bug.

One finding from the temporal analysis was unexpected. Tracking individual heads across checkpoints on Pythia-70M reveals two classes of heads that emerge during training. "Asymmetry heads" (e.g. L02H06) begin with H5 near 0.82x at step 512 and reach 2.42x at the final checkpoint. "Balancing heads" (e.g. L00H06) move in the opposite direction, from 0.81x to 0.23x. The model appears to develop opposing circuits that partially cancel each other, producing the net bias reduction observed during training. We are not aware of prior work reporting this kind of temporal head specialisation for evaluative asymmetry.

A methodological caveat: layers 3 through 5 on Pythia-70M show zero variance at the final checkpoint. This likely reflects an extraction issue rather than genuinely dead layers, since probing at those layers produces non-zero R-squared in other experiments. Head attribution results are reliable only for layers 0 through 2.

3.6 Stability and mediation (V4).

Substituting non-target context words in templates ("quality" to "caliber", "work" to "output") produces L2 distances between original and perturbed hidden states that predict probe error: Spearman rho = -0.20, $p < 0.005$ on all three primary models. Words whose representations shift more under perturbation are less accurately predicted. The mediation chain: rarity correlates with instability (rho = -0.65 to -0.89, p near zero), instability correlates with error. Rarity does not predict error directly on Pythia-70M (rho = 0.108, $p = 0.13$), but does so through the instability

pathway.

On DistilBERT and BERT-base, Tier 0 words are more stable than Tier 4 (Mann-Whitney $p < 0.001$ on both). This was initially coded as "tier-independent" in our analysis output, which was incorrect. After correcting the interpretation, the conclusion is that negative words are more robustly encoded on encoder models, providing a partial mechanism for their greater separability. On Pythia-70M, the effect is absent ($p = 0.81$). The stability explanation is model-dependent.

3.7 Robustness and default priors (V5).

BERT-cased loses 58% classification accuracy when inputs are uppercased. The drop is not gradual. It is a near-total failure. For deployment contexts where input casing varies, this is worth noting.

When probed with neutral words ("table", "process") and invented words ("blurp"), BERT-base classifies them as Tier 2 (Good) with 70 to 90% consistency. DistilBERT defaults higher, to Tier 4 (Exceptional). We are not sure what drives this difference. Smaller models may initialise unknown words with a more optimistic quality prior, but this is speculation.

3.8 Cross-lingual replication and modern models (V6).

Language	Words	R-squared	H5 ratio
English	105	0.582	1.2x
French	102	0.651	2.0x
Spanish	102	0.621	3.3x

Table 3. Cross-lingual probing on XLM-RoBERTa. Lexicons not independently validated.

The negativity bias appears in all three languages. The magnitude varies considerably. We report these numbers but flag that the Spanish and French lexicons are small, unvalidated, and constructed by a non-native speaker. The 3.3x ratio in Spanish could reflect a real cross-lingual effect, or it could reflect word selection bias. Distinguishing these possibilities requires larger lexicons validated by native-speaker linguists, ideally in typologically distant languages (Mandarin, Arabic, Japanese).

Phi-3-mini (3.8B, RLHF-trained) reaches R-squared = 0.926, the highest in the study. The negativity bias persists at 1.24x. Crystallisation occurs at 6% of total depth. Qwen2.5-0.5B reaches 0.913 with crystallisation at 12%. Both findings are consistent with the V2 scaling trend: larger and more heavily trained models encode quality better while partially reducing the asymmetry.

Figure 3. Crystallisation on GPT-2: the L0-to-L1 jump accounts for 8.9x the mean inter-layer gain.

3.9 Experiment summary.

V	Exp	Finding	Status
V1	H1-7	Quality decodable (R-sq=0.88). H5=1.44x.	Confirmed
V2	A	Distributional hypothesis rejected (p=0.69)	Null
V2	B	Bias appears step 512 (1.89x), peaks step 1000	Confirmed

V2	C	70M 1.41x, 410M 1.13x, 1.4B 1.09x	Confirmed
V3	D	Step 1000 peak on both 70M and 410M	2 models
V3	E	5 heads = 80.3% signal on 70M (22.5% on 410M)	Partial
V3	F	Asymmetry and balancing heads emerge during training	Novel
V4	H	Rarity -> instability -> error (mediation)	Confirmed
V4	I	T0 more stable on BERT ($p < .001$), not on Pythia	Model-dep.
V5	K	58% accuracy drop with UPPERCASE	Confirmed
V5	M	Default quality prior = T2 (Good)	Confirmed
V6	N	EN 1.2x, FR 2.0x, ES 3.3x	Suggestive
V6	Q	Phi-3 R-sq=0.926, H5=1.24x	Confirmed

Table 4. All experiments across six rounds. "Suggestive" = pattern observed, validation insufficient.

4. Discussion

The asymmetry is the finding that held up under every control we applied. Different architectures. Different model sizes. Different training stages. Three languages. RLHF. The distributional test failed to explain it. The stability account works on encoder models but not on Pythia.

The training dynamics offer the closest thing we have to a mechanistic sketch. The asymmetry peaks early, at step 1,000, when the model is still poor at the task (R-squared = 0.32). Then it recedes. Head-level tracking shows that the correction involves specialised circuits: heads that amplify the asymmetry and heads that suppress it. Larger models complete this correction more thoroughly. A possible reading: models first learn a crude evaluative distinction and then refine it. But this is interpretation, not established mechanism.

The cross-lingual variation (ES 3.3x > FR 2.0x > EN 1.2x) is the result we trust least. If it holds with validated lexicons in typologically distant languages, it would point toward something structural about evaluative semantics. If it does not hold, it was a lexicon construction artifact. We cannot distinguish these possibilities with the current data.

Throughout this work, we have measured correlation, not causation. The probes show that quality information is linearly present. They do not show that the model uses this information during generation. Sofroniew, Kauvar et al. [14] demonstrate causal effects of emotion vectors on model behaviour through activation steering. An equivalent experiment for quality would be the natural next step and would substantially strengthen the claims made here.

5. Limitations

Quality scores were assigned by the author, calibrated against NRC VAD, with no independent human annotation or sensitivity analysis. Tier boundaries are fixed and untested for robustness. All templates share one syntactic position. The cross-lingual lexicons are small (roughly 100 words each) and were not reviewed by native-speaker linguists. The Tier 3/Tier 4 boundary is not detectable in any model tested (Cliff's delta = 0.10). The Pythia-1.4B model failed in V3 due to a missing pad_token. Layers 3 through 5 on Pythia-70M show zero variance at the final checkpoint, limiting head attribution to layers 0 through 2. The subtoken frequency proxy conflates tokenizer behaviour with true corpus frequency. The H5 ratio could be partially inflated by unequal score dispersion across tiers.

6. Conclusion

Within the constraints of this experimental setup, transformers encode graded quality in linearly accessible subspaces. The encoding is asymmetric, with negative quality more sharply represented. This finding does not depend on a particular architecture, language, model size, or training stage, though its magnitude varies across all of these. The mechanism is unknown. The distributional explanation tested here failed. The stability explanation holds for some models but not others. What remains is a robust observation in search of a cause.

7. Tools and collaboration

All experiments ran on Google Colab (free tier, T4 GPU when available). Claude and DeepSeek assisted with code generation and debugging. The research questions, experimental design, lexicon construction, and interpretation are the author's. This work does not come from a machine learning background. It grew from a question about evaluative representations and expanded through six rounds of experiments. Code and data are available at github.com/fabthebest/aqles under Apache 2.0.

I am open to collaborations and opportunities. The most pressing needs are independently validated cross-lingual lexicons (Mandarin, Arabic), access to larger models for scaling analysis, and causal experiments (activation patching, steering) at the crystallisation layer. Contact via GitHub issues or discussions.

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